

LITERATURE REVIEW ON SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

The effective and systematic waste management is a challenging task for residential and non residential sector. It is proved that Industrial sector contribute much for the waste generation, at the same time can't ignore the contribution of residential waste to the total waste generation. The prime focus must be on Waste reduction and reuse at generation point which lead to curbing of waste generation in the initial stage itself, thereby contributes to the minimisation of total waste generation at macro level. This paper is based on background study of waste management in different areas and concluding with finding out the research gap with regarding to residential waste management.

Keywords: waste generation, domestic waste, waste reduction and reuse.

INTRODUCTION

WASTE is any material, which is no more needed by the owner. Waste is the thing which doesn't have any value in the eyes of man but Waste can be a wealthy gift or lifetime sin depending upon how it is treated. Nature has provided plenty of resources, it is the responsibility of human being to use it wisely and keep it safe for next generation.

Waste is any substances or objects, which are disposed of or are intended to be disposed of or are required to be disposed of by the provisions of national law [1]. There are numerous classification waste based on their nature, the Sources of MSW (Municipal Solid Waste) can be mainly categorised as two parts i.e, Residential waste and Non residential waste. Non residential waste again sub classified as institutional waste, industrial waste, and commercial waste [2]. Further medical waste, E- waste, degradable and non- degradable waste, solid waste, liquid waste, hazardous waste, non- hazardous waste, animal waste, dry waste, wet waste, recyclable waste and many more [3]. All kinds of waste generates at home, i.e., solid, liquid, hazardous, medical waste etc [4]. E-Waste is generating rapidly due to modest technology in all the fields and vast usage and attraction towards electronic gadgets. E- Waste proved to be a hazardous waste because of its harsh chemical content involved in it [5]. Plastic waste is the major waste in solid waste composition. Next to industry, household is the major users of plastic materials [6]. Rapid urbanisation, modernisation, improved infrastructure are the major reasons for rapid waste generation [7]. Based on the data available for a few cities, it seems that the biodegradable component would be somewhere between 55 and 60 per cent on an annual basis [8]. In Kyoto, food loss is approximately 40% of total waste, of which leftovers and unused food account for about 40% in both households and business sector [9].

Source: waste to resources: A waste management handbook [10].

Residential degradable waste and recyclable waste can be reused at domestic level for the secondary usage.

Objectives:

- To identify the types of waste, problems connected with waste management and measures to resolve it.
- To identify the current status of domestic waste management
- To do exhaustive literature review on waste management
- To identify the research gap with regard to Domestic waste management.

Study Methods:

The literature review focuses on surveying information pertaining to existing waste management methodologies, policies, and research. Exhaustive literature review regarding the concept and theories has been done through collecting latest Journals from Google Scholar. This article is based on Secondary data, which has been collected from various sources like books, reputed journals, conference proceedings, websites magazine and newspapers.

Purpose

The purpose of this literature review is to gain an understanding of waste management planning concepts, frameworks, strategies, and components that are current and emerging in the field. A particular focus is given to literature which pertains to the management of municipal solid waste.

Obstacles for effective waste management

India faces major environmental problems associated with waste generation and inadequate waste collection, transport, treatment and disposal. Current waste management systems in India cannot cope with the volumes of waste generated by an increasing urban population [11].It has been

observed that the plastic waste from the houses are collected with other solid wastes and stored. People used to dispose waste at approved dumping bins. Very less portion of the respondents used to bury the waste. Few people used to throw to the open space [6]. 60 %of the households dispose their domestic waste by throwing into open spaces. Food waste the highest waste generation at household level in kuttar and manjanadi village [12].land filling is still a major issue in developing countries [13].which lead to spreading waste near the bin which adversely effects the health of the people. The systematic and scientific waste disposal is still a challenging task in particular areas of Zambia [4]. Even though the landfilling sites are discovered still the acceptance from the public is a major challenge because of its negative impact on health, the acceptance by the people depends on the degree of awareness, knowledge and guidance given to them [13].The study has been conducted in Zambia by considering low, moderate and high populated areas. it is shocking result that majority (52%) are unaware of waste segregation, availability of community bins are not of appropriate size and time schedule for clearing the waste from bins are not appreciable one[4]. It is observed that the current scenario of solid waste management is not adequate. The medium and small scale towns are not much serious about effective solid waste disposal. MSWM Rule 2000 is not up to the mark in solving the problems of SW. It is because of funding issue, lack of awareness and guidance, lack of coordination [14]. In most populated cities of Bangladesh, it is difficult to the govt authorities to manage socio environmental problem with the present human resource, infrastructure, economic support etc [15].Many statistical information proved in that the rapid urbanisation lead to the rapid increase in the waste generation [16].The major obstacle lies with long distance to community bin, lack of community bins and rigid time schedule of collection of waste [6]. Not only urban areas but also village faces problems in collection, storage, segregation, treatment and disposal of waste. In village, household waste, agricultural waste, animal waste increased the accumulation of solid waste [17]. Mixed storage and collection of materials in the same container leads to the serious problem. There is a need to separate storage of waste collection depending upon the nature of the waste [18]. Lack of knowledge, ineffective technique, inadequate finance, unaccountability are the major obstacles for the systematic SWM in India [16]. 1,43,449 tonnes per day (TPD) of MSW was generated in India during 2014–2015, with an average waste of 0.11 kilogram (kg)/capita/day. Of the total MSW, approximately 1,17,644 TPD (80%) was collected, while only 32,871 TPD (22%) was processed or treated. [19].

Source: Collection vs Dumped Statistics (numbers in million MT per annum) [20]

There is a huge gap between the waste generation, collection and treatment, which endangers the environment as well as the negative impact on the health.

Adverse effect of improper waste management

Societal health is directly influenced by the waste management in that particular region [21]. Ineffective waste disposal not only have adverse effect on health of the people but also turn out to be environmental hazardous [22]. Majority of the residents are tensed about the improper waste disposal which leads to negative impact on the health. but minority of the respondents treat it as a serious issue [21].Solid waste contribute around 22%of total green gas emission in India [23]. If the population increased in a rapid way it would be 300 million waste per year, around 1450km of land is needed to dispose by 2051[16].

Techniques applied for Effective Waste Management

The qualitative and quantitative study has been undertaken to identify the constraints and challenges encountered by the residents of Malaysia in household waste segregation [7]. Descriptive cross sectional survey was conducted to collect the information from the households [21]. Sources of waste in a desktop approach [24]. The appropriate land filling sites can be identified by Geographical Information System (GIS) tools. i.e. MIPM,MCD,MCE,WLC,AHP and FMCDM through two step sequential approach, multi-indices evaluation, Boolean approaches, spatil analysis[13]. Fuzzy set theory is suitable while there is uncertainty in selecting the preferred area and it has the capabilities in representing vague qualitative data [13]. financial areas of solid waste management is focused through cost- benefit analysis of SWM, Environmental audit of SWM, centralised and decentralised system of SWM [25]. Landfill gas-to-energy plants, Thermal treatment, Anaerobic digestion, Vermi-composting, Aerobic composting etc are the environmental friendly measures to treat the SW. The role of rag pickers have been highlighted. Around 14% of the budget of the municipality saved by the rag pickers. Various guidelines and polices have been implemented by the government of India with regard to SWM [16]. Seasonal difference in the generation of municipal solid waste in the city of Guwahti. Two years field study has been conducted to identify the monthly and seasonal

differentiation in the quantum of MSW generation. it has been observed that the generation of organic waste (more than 50%) is more than the other kind of waste in the said area. and in the month of January to march and October to December food waste generation was numerous because of festival seasons. the generation of coal and wood waste was highest in winter season , it found that a nominal variation in the generation of plastic, paper, glass waste, animal waste etc in the whole year. because some of recyclable waste were sold to the recyclable centres[26]. The problem connected with waste management are categorised at various stages i.e., generation, storage, transportation, processing, recovery and disposal [27]. Focused on the quantum and quality of solid waste management in major medium scale and small scale cities of India and categorised class 1 to 4 towns. It has been identified that very less quantity of paper, plastic and glass are recycled because of its secondary use at domestic level and at street vending [14]."Three R" approach (reduce, reuse, recycle) is the best remedy for the solid waste treatment[28] there is seasonal variation in the collection of waste depending upon the necessity to use, lifestyle, taste and preferences, economic conditions etc [26].The personal details(age, sex, education) doesn't influence towards waste segregation [7].

Source: TIMES OF INDIA march 4, 2020[29]

The future of India with regard to waste management is in a critical condition compared to other nations. It is the need of the hour to implement effective measures to resolve the problem of SWM.

Awareness level

People are not much aware about the reuse, reduce, compost and recovery concept of waste. But people are keen interested towards reducing and reusing the waste if proper guidance and instructions are given by government agencies [22]. Private sector involvement is more in middle and high income groups compared to low income groups [30].

Measures/ Suggestions

People and govt are now serious regarding SMW in comparisons to decades back [31]. In order to give a push to the municipal solid waste management in cities, the Ministry of Urban Development launched the Swachh Bharat Mission(SBM) in 2014. SBM seeks to promote cities

as engines of economic growth through improvement in the quality of urban infrastructure, with assured service levels and efficient governance. SBM aims to address the challenges in management of municipal solid waste and to support cities in developing modern and appropriate systems [32]. Solid Waste Management Rules (2016) provide a reasonable framework to address the multiple challenges of municipal solid waste management in India [33]. The success of waste management depends on the collaborative efforts of the citizens, government authorities, and private sectors [22]. Environmental safety education and awareness is must to achieve environmental sustainability in long [30]. The private sector has the highest contribution towards waste collection and disposal in Nigeria. It is necessary to boost private sector more in that region to achieve environmental sustainability [30]. Strict surveillance is required for abolishing open space waste disposal, disposal to rivers, gutter, and drains and the law prevailing on waste management should be popularised, private public partnership is needed [12]. Various government regulations were in support of effective and hygienic waste management [14]. The challenge of waste disposal can be faced by giving timely and continuous awareness regarding, reducing the usage of plastic and recycling of the plastic waste. The system of R3 must be followed. i.e., reduce, reuse, and recycle [6]. With improved facility of waste disposal near to each houses will definitely lead to the appropriate waste segregation by each households. The effective waste segregation can be achieved by the action of responsible citizens. The governmental and non governmental agencies play a crucial role in educating, training, monitoring, guiding the citizens in accomplishing the goal of effective waste segregation [7]. There was a mixed opinion regarding the responsibility of waste disposal i.e, some opinioned that it is the government responsibility, peoples responsibility, and resident sole responsibility to keep their soundings clean and tidy [21]. Rather than disposal of waste there should be management of waste. Private companies role in SWM is phenomenon, i.e., SPML (Subhash Projects and Marketing Limited) provide complete solution to waste collection, segregation, transportation, recycling of all the types of waste. HCL Company believes that the e-waste is their responsibility and various measures have been taken to recycle the e-waste. Plasma Thermal Destruction Recovery (PTDR) technology is an environmental friendly process, that converts wastes into non-toxic synthetic gas (which is a valuable source of alternative energy) and other useful end-products. Strict regulation must be implemented for the sustainability of environment. Without segregation of waste at generation point, it is highly impossible to achieve 100% waste management in India. To prevent any disease caused by waste, it is an urgent need for the systematic and scientific strategic plan of action on waste management [34]. It is important to involve Non govt agencies to create awareness among the people which govt alone can't do it. The active private public partnership is must [31]. MSWM rules of 2000 are briefly explains i.e, door to door collection, community bins, schedules for collection of waste. Dividing collection point as a slums and commercial areas and also degradable and non degradable waste [14]. It is advised that existing storage practice must be converted to well hygiene secondary disposal sites. Current final disposal sites need to be improved by sanitary landfill technique in the existing sites [15]. The major cities have been communalised the composting of MSW. The attractive incentives have been given to the private sector to boost the production of marketable compost. Education to the people, complete and clear cut instructions regarding various process of waste management, compulsory segregation of different kinds of waste, food waste must be stored in a container with lid, street cleaning should be strictly followed, dumping sites must be away from habitation etc [27].

Recycling, Aerobic composting, anaerobic composting, waste to energy combustion, sanitary land fillings are the advisable treatment for the solid waste management in villages. Waste to energy is the best option to avoid waste and also to fulfil the need of electricity in the village. It is advisable that developing prototype model for the proper treatment of solid waste in village is the need of the day [17]. The pressure of growing MSW as a result of industrialization, urbanization and economic growth. Source separation is the best approach to waste management to reduce the burden of waste disposals [35]. Manual separation of different Variety of waste is appreciable one. Compulsory segregation of waste is needed in public places also. Expenditure on transportation of waste must economised [36]. Focus should be given to small and medium towns with regard to solid waste management as 71% of the total population are residing that areas [14]. The need for the private public partnership with regard to MSW. Much statistical information proved in that the rapid urbanisation lead to the rapid increase in the waste generation [16]. Government support should also be product-based [32]. The effective implementation of needs-based training, awareness programmes taking females as one of the main audience groups and determination of municipality needs are thereby highly recommendable [37].

Impact of systematic waste management

Waste management lead to better standard of living of the people by reducing the cost of 418 per ton from 1000 per ton. Reduction in waste disposal would result in lower carbon footprint in future [23]. High recommendation to the recycle process to manage the waste, as it not only contributes to the waste management but also income to the government or the private sector who involved in recycling business [38]. It creates industries thereby contributing to the employment generation [28]. Effective and hygiene waste management leads to positive impact on health of the people as well as environment as a whole.

Future plan of action in India

Governmental and Non-Governmental agencies have initiated various action plans towards waste management as a future goal. Goa government insisted urban local bodies and village panchayath to implement the ban on single use plastics from March 31, 2021 and directed to impose penalties in case of breach of law [39]. Sources in BBMP said it is spending a lot on waste management, Rs 1,000 crore, which reduces the investment in infrastructure in cities. Only 50 crore per year is accumulated for waste management through tax. But the spending is double of the tax collected [40]. Mangalore City Corporation planning to start different collection centre for dry waste, after the successful implementation of dry waste collection centre at Ullal city in collaboration with Hasiru Dala and APD foundation [41]. Haridwar Municipal Corporation planning to collect on average 10 to 15 Rupees per Room as solid waste charges to meet the huge expenses of solid waste treatment. Every year huge number of pilgrims are visiting Haridwar, they are directly contributing to the generation of huge waste [42]. Noida state government has prepared 3 years action plan for the waste management in the city, as city generates 300 metric tonnes of waste per day. . i.e, gobar gas at village, construction of waste management plant, construction public toilets, planning to launch mobile apps for the garbage collection in the city [43]. Hyderabad government planning to build 1000 toilets over the city [44]. Civic body of Chennai, made a blueprint of different categories of taxes, fees and impositions to the citizens based on their house areas, commercial space and public gatherings [45]. Indhira Gandhi National Open University,

New Delhi started a unique course on waste management after PUC, minimum duration the course is 6 months covering the aspects of different types waste, health impacts, managing waste in a profitable way, responsibilities of citizen in waste management etc, to train the young minds with regard to systematic waste management.[46]. IIT Kharagpur Research, Kolkatta framed various incentive policy for adopting eco-friendly bio plastics, biodegradable materials with higher recyclability. Artificial Intelligence-powered sustainable technologies can be deployed to manage efficient sorting and recycling of waste. This shall be further supported by means of "refuse, reduce, reuse and recycle" mantra of the circular economy implemented in post Covid environment [47] Greater Chennai Corporation gave licence to 21 companies to deal with waste. Conversion of waste into wealth is the task assigned to the companies [48]. Chandigarh MC, formed a civic body committee to collect waste from different sectors in Twin-bin vehicle, the concept of twin bin vehicle introduced to compulsory waste segregation at generation point, penalty imposed on the defaulter [49]. Focus must be on ZERO-WASTE society concept [50].

Research Gap and conclusion:

From the exhaustive literature study on waste management it has been proved that, even though there is a sincere efforts from governmental and non governmental agencies regarding proper waste segregation and treatment, it is not up to the mark. Rather than concentrating on waste treatment after its collection, it is advisable to reduce the waste generation at the generation point itself. It is necessary to follow R3 rules for the minimisation waste at generation point. i.e, at households. The further research should be based on "DOMESTIC WASTE REDUCTION AND REUSE PRACTICES/ MANAGEMENT". To identify the obstacles faced by the households to follow R3 rules, governmental and non - governmental support for the waste management at household levels through various motivational programmes.

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